

Prospective German Language Teachers' Perceptions of Germans

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Abstract: A review of the current literature uncovers a significant gap in studies examining prospective German language teachers' perceptions of the target language and culture. Therefore, this study aims to address both theoretical and pedagogical gaps by exploring their perceptions of Germans through semi-structured interviews. A total of 21 prospective German language teachers enrolled at a Turkish state university in central Anatolia participated, and the data were analyzed using content analysis procedures. Findings reveal that participants view Germany as appealing due to its education system, economic prosperity, and quality of life. However, they also express concerns about racism, social distance, climate, and language difficulties. Through the identification of 81 codes, two main themes emerged: "Positive views about Germany" and "Negative views about Germany." The results suggest that these perceptions have a significant impact on language learning motivation and teacher identity. This study highlights the importance of raising awareness of stereotypes in culture-based language teaching and offers a theoretical basis for future research. Additionally, the study emphasizes that cultural and social interactions play a crucial role in shaping prospective German teachers' mental images of other countries.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Almanya algıları
Almanca öğrenenler
Almanca öğretmen
adayları,
Kültürel temsiller
Kültürlerarası
farkındalık

Almanca Öğretmeni Adaylarının Almanlara Yönelik Algıları

Özet: Mevcut literatürün gözden geçirilmesi, Almanca öğretmen adaylarının hedef dil ve kültüre ilişkin algılarını inceleyen çalışmaların önemli ölçüde eksik olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Bu nedenle, bu çalışma hem kuramsal hem de pedagojik boşlukları doldurmayı amaçlamakta ve öğretmen adaylarının Almanlara yönelik algılarını yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler yoluyla incelemektedir. Araştırmaya, İç Anadolu'da bir devlet üniversitesinde öğrenim gören toplam 21 Almanca öğretmen adayı katılmıştır ve veriler içerik analizi yöntemiyle değerlendirilmiştir. Bulgular, katılımcıların Almanya'yı eğitim sistemi, ekonomik refahı ve yaşam kalitesi açısından çekici bulduklarını göstermektedir. Ancak, aynı zamanda ırkçılık, mesafeli sosyal ilişkiler, iklim ve dil zorlukları gibi konularda da endişelerini dile getirmişlerdir. Toplam 81 kodun belirlenmesiyle "Almanya hakkında olumlu görüşler" ve "Almanya hakkında olumsuz görüşler" olmak üzere iki ana tema ortaya çıkmıştır. Sonuçlar, bu algıların dil öğrenme motivasyonu ve öğretmen kimliği gelişimini etkilediğini göstermektedir. Bu çalışma, kültür temelli dil öğretiminde stereotip farkındalığının artırılmasının önemine dikkat çekmekte ve gelecekteki araştırmalar için kuramsal bir temel sunmaktadır. Ayrıca çalışma, kültürel ve toplumsal etkileşimlerin Almanca öğretmen adaylarının diğer ülkelere dair zihinsel imgelerini şekillendirmede kritik bir rol oynadığını vurgulamaktadır.

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1. Introduction

Over the course of a hundred years of diplomatic relations between Turkey and Germany, profound cultural interactions have developed across various fields, including art, education, cooperation, and scientific exchange. These interactions have played a crucial role in shaping Turkish society's perceptions of Germany and German culture. In particular, Germany's historical rapprochement with the Ottoman Empire and its reputation as a reliable ally and partner provide a meaningful context for understanding the origins of these perceptions (Güngördü, 2019). Official diplomatic relations, formally established on March 3, 1924, after periods of interruption, were further consolidated through the involvement of German experts who came to Turkey to contribute their expertise in various domains (Aydın, 2017). Academics who fled Germany due to political unrest played a pivotal role in establishing German studies faculties at universities in Ankara and Istanbul, thereby further expanding cultural and academic exchange (Tapan & Kuruyazıcı, 2020). Today, these historical and academic ties are reflected in the German teacher training programs at sixteen different universities in Turkey, which continue to advance the quality and scope of German language instruction.

This long-standing historical and cultural exchange has laid the foundation for the emergence of distinct perceptions of Germany within Turkish society. The present study aims to investigate the impact of these perceptions on the educational process by examining in depth the kinds of images prospective German teachers in Turkey hold about Germany, whether these perceptions are positive or negative, and which views are most prevalent. By providing a detailed classification of these perceptions, the study aims to illuminate an area often neglected in the existing literature. In particular, there is a notable lack of research focused on the perspective of German learners in Turkey. By examining the perceptions of Germany among prospective teachers and the influence of these perceptions on the educational process, this research addresses a significant gap. It contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how such views impact both teaching and learning.

A review of the literature reveals that both Turkish and German literature frequently portray the images of Germans and Turks in a negative light (Çakır, 2012). Notable examples include the negative depiction of Turks in the works of certain German authors and the similarly negative portrayal of Germany in writings by Turkish authors such as Yüksel Pazarkaya (Kocadoru, 2004). However, there is a distinct lack of research analyzing the perspectives of Turkish students who are learning German. While international research has addressed the role of learner attitudes and stereotypes in foreign language acquisition (Kramsch, 1993; Garrett, 2010), studies specifically examining the perceptions of Turkish learners toward the German language and culture remain scarce. Most research to date has emphasized the importance of cultural images and attitudes in shaping learners' motivation and educational outcomes (Dörnyei & Csizér, 2002). This study thus addresses an underexplored context by focusing on the multifaceted mental representations of Germany held by prospective German teachers in Turkey, providing new insights into a topic that has been rarely examined in detail.

The significance of this research lies in its focus on the perceptions of German learners, a perspective seldom investigated in the existing literature. By filling this gap, the study offers a deeper understanding of the impact of stereotypical perceptions of Germany on the educational process. It enables the development of concrete recommendations for enhancing teaching methodology based on these findings.

The primary objective of this study is to identify the perceptions that prospective German teachers in Turkey hold about Germany, to determine whether these perceptions are predominantly positive or negative, and to determine the most prevalent perceptions in order to analyze their impact on the educational process. Given the scarcity of research from the perspective of German learners, this study aims to fill this gap and thereby make a meaningful contribution to the field. The research questions guiding this study are as follows:

1. What perceptions do prospective German teachers in Turkey have about Germany?
2. Are these perceptions positive or negative?
3. What are the most common and prominent perceptions about Germany among student teachers, and how do these perceptions affect the educational process?

1.1. Literature Review

1.1.1. *The Relations between Turkey and Germany*

The relationship between Turkey and Germany is deeply rooted in history and marked by its complexity. Diplomatic contacts began as early as 1718, with the Ottoman Empire's correspondence to Prussian King Wilhelm I (Özgüldür, 1993), and were later strengthened by the countries' joint involvement in World War I. Subsequent cooperation during World War II further reinforced these connections. Following the establishment of the Republic of Turkey, bilateral diplomatic and economic relations were consolidated through a series of agreements, including the 1924 Friendship Agreement, the Consular Agreement of 1929, and the Trade Agreement of 1930 (Armaoğlu, 2009).

After the devastation of World War II, Germany experienced a period of rapid economic recovery known as the 'economic miracle', primarily facilitated by the Marshall Plan (Kocaman Wilutzki, 2023). Between 1955 and 1968, Germany, having emerged as Europe's industrial powerhouse, signed a series of intergovernmental labor agreements with Mediterranean countries to address its growing labor demand (Genel, 2014). In this context, a bilateral labor agreement was signed between the embassies of Ankara and Bonn on October 31, 1961. This agreement formally regulated labor migration from Turkey to Germany and represented a pivotal step in the countries' relationship (Canver, 2008). The resulting wave of labor migration had a profound impact on Turkish-German relations, forging bonds between the two societies that extended well beyond the level of interstate diplomacy and resulted in long-lasting societal transformation. Educational and cultural exchanges were also promoted through the arrival of German scholars in Turkey during the 1920s and 1930s, as well as through Turkish students pursuing higher education in Germany (Özil, 2013). These exchanges directly influenced the motivation for bilateral agreements and deepened academic and cultural ties.

The rise of the National Socialist Party in Germany in 1933 prompted many academics and intellectuals to flee Nazi persecution. A significant number of these scholars found refuge in Turkey, where they made substantial contributions to Turkish universities, the arts, and broader cultural life (Kreiser & Neumann, 2009). These émigrés, welcomed especially at Istanbul University, Ankara University, and other academic institutions, played a crucial role in Turkey's scientific transformation and modernization (Hekimler, 2023). By sharing their knowledge and expertise, they not only enriched Turkey's academic landscape but also actively participated in modernization projects, strengthening the human dimension of Turkish-German relations and fostering connections at the societal level.

During this period, German language departments were established for the first time at Ankara University's Faculty of Language, History and Geography (1935–36) and Istanbul University's Faculty of Letters (1942), marking significant progress in linguistic and literary education (Tapan & Kuruyazıcı, 2020). Today, the cumulative experience of human mobility and exchange between Turkey and Germany has produced a uniquely deep and enduring relationship that transcends political and economic ties. Hence, apart from Germany and the Ottoman Empire's close relations during World War I, the events of the 1930s and 1940s made Germany and Germans even more noticeable in the daily discourses of the Turkish people.

1.1.2. Teaching German as a Foreign Language in Turkey

The introduction of foreign language instruction in secondary schools during the Tanzimat era marked a significant turning point for language education in Turkey. The establishment of the Galatasaray Lycée in 1868 under French guidance introduced a Westernized curriculum, positioning French as the primary language of instruction and setting the stage for the subsequent prominence of European languages—such as French, German, and English—in the Ottoman educational system (Davison, 1961). Over time, a series of educational reforms have been implemented to improve the quality of foreign language teaching, reflecting the ongoing evolution of Turkey's education system and the shifting priorities regarding language instruction for students. Notably, the 1933 educational reform abolished the Darülfünun and established Istanbul University, where departments of Western philology were founded within the Faculty of Literature (Tapan & Kuruyazıcı, 2020).

Until the late 1980s, English, German, and French were commonly taught as foreign languages in Turkey. However, subsequent policy changes led to the removal of German and French from the curriculum in favor of a single foreign language. The status and importance of German as a foreign language have fluctuated in response to major educational reforms and evolving language policy frameworks. The 1997 law mandating eight years of compulsory education, along with increased alignment with European Union language policies, renewed interest in German and French as secondary foreign languages (Commission of the European Communities, 2003; Tinsley & Board, 2013). Since the 2012–2013 academic year, English instruction has begun as early as the second grade of primary school. This early exposure to English lays a foundation for studying additional foreign languages in middle school (Balci, 2016). As Akıllılar (2013) points out, language education in Turkey is typically not conducted within a multilingual context—foreign language teaching is primarily equated with English language teaching. Although the expansion of English instruction in primary schools is a significant milestone, a broader historical perspective reveals the noteworthy position and development of German language teaching in Turkey.

Historically, Arabic and Persian were widely used in Turkey, while Latin, Greek, and Italian served diplomatic functions. French emerged as the dominant European language in the eighteenth century as relations with France intensified. German language instruction began at the Naval Academy in 1773 and was further expanded during the Ottoman period with the establishment of a language school in 1864 (Demirel, 2021). In the nineteenth century, German became a compulsory subject at the military academy as a result of strengthened political ties between Germany and Turkey (Can, 2020). German was introduced into the curriculum of the Language Institute, established in 1820 within the Office of the Interpreter (Bab-ı Ali Tercüme Odası), and was formally added by decree of Sultan Abdülhamid II in 1892 (Balci, 2008). The curricular reforms of 1933 further emphasized the importance of German language education, establishing institutions such as Istanbul University's School of

Foreign Languages, Gazi Pedagogical Institute, and Istanbul German High School as leading centers for German language instruction in Turkey (Demirel, 2021).

Following World War II, departments dedicated to German language teaching were established at Turkish universities in 1947 (Altunya, 2006). The first Departments of German Language and Literature were founded at Ankara University's Faculty of Language, History, and Geography (1935–36) and Istanbul University's Faculty of Letters (1942), laying the foundation for the discipline in Turkey (Tapan & Kuruyazıcı, 2020). During the early 1980s, significant changes in higher education policy, including the establishment of the Higher Education Council (YÖK), led to the reorganization of German language and literature departments under the umbrella of Western Languages, with curricula redesigned in accordance with YÖK's joint programs (Tapan & Kuruyazıcı, 2020). Since the 2012–2013 academic year, compulsory second foreign language courses have been included in the curricula of Anatolian and science high schools (Karaman, 2017). Across Europe, German is frequently chosen as a second foreign language, reflecting both historical ties and policies promoting linguistic diversity (Cenoz & Gorter, 2011). Cenoz and Gorter (2011) found that students' decisions regarding second foreign language study are shaped by social, economic, and institutional factors, with German often prioritized due to its perceived value in education and career advancement. Following the 2012/2013 educational reform, perceptions of the German language in Turkey have shifted (Balci, 2016). The German language has experienced considerable growth in instruction, with increasing popularity in recent years. This trend is supported by the presence of German teacher education departments at sixteen universities, German language and literature departments at thirteen universities, and translation studies programs at eight universities (Üstün & Tanrıkulu, 2023).

1.1.3. Perceptions of Germans by the Turks

While this study initially focused on the perceptions of Germany and Germans among Turkish German teacher candidates, it is essential to recognize that such perceptions, when collectively shared and reinforced over time, can solidify into stereotypes. Stereotypes are widely defined as sets of beliefs or generalizations about the characteristics, attributes, and behaviors of members of certain groups; these beliefs are often oversimplified and do not necessarily reflect reality (Dovidio et al., 2010). The process of stereotyping involves attributing a fixed set of traits to all members of a group, serving as a rationale for prejudice or discriminatory behavior. Thus, repeatedly encountered and socially reinforced perceptions may crystallize into enduring stereotypes, shaping how individuals evaluate and interact with members of other groups.

The concept of stereotype is closely related to the mental representations that individuals develop when constructing an image of their social environment and others within it. Initial impressions are often shaped by social categories and the stereotypes associated with them, making it crucial to understand the processes underlying impression formation (Krieglmeyer & Sherman, 2012). Stereotypes are widely recognized as cognitive structures that reflect individuals' attitudes and feelings toward social groups, and they remain a central topic in the social sciences (Dovidio et al., 2010). Abrams (2002) emphasizes that stereotypes cannot be separated from human cognition and cultural frameworks, laying the foundation for subsequent empirical research that situates stereotypes within cognitive and psychological structures (Spencer-Rodgers, 2001). As Allport (1954) noted, stereotypes are not exclusively negative; they can be neutral or even positive, functioning as psychological tools to manage the overwhelming influx of information. Although the term is often used synonymously with prejudice in everyday language, in the context of foreign language education, it acquires a

more nuanced meaning. Nikitina et al. (2022) define stereotypes in this setting as how foreign language learners conceptualize the target language's culture, society, and people. However, a review of the literature suggests that research on stereotypes in the context of foreign language education remains scarce, particularly in the Turkish context. Database searches on the Web of Science, DergiPark, and other scholarly platforms confirm that studies on this topic are limited and have yet to be thoroughly explored. Consequently, investigating the mental representations of target language communities among foreign language learners offers the potential to address important theoretical and pedagogical gaps.

Research examining the effects of stereotypes in foreign language teaching highlights the intricate web of cultural, social, and cognitive influences encountered throughout the language acquisition process. For example, Sayer and Meadows (2012) use derogatory remarks about Mexicans in the BBC program *Top Gear* to illustrate how national stereotypes are perpetuated by the media, suggesting that such content can serve as a pedagogical tool for promoting critical thinking and cultural awareness in the classroom. Similarly, Işık et al. (2024) examined the stereotypes held by university students in Northern Cyprus during language learning, demonstrating that perceptions are influenced by variables such as gender, age, education, and language proficiency. Such findings underscore the significant role of individual differences in shaping stereotypes.

Studies within the framework of stereotype threat theory further reveal the direct impact of such biases on individual performance. For instance, Paladino et al. (2009) found that Italian female students from Alto Adige/South Tyrol performed worse on German language tests when reminded of negative stereotypes about themselves. Bedyńska et al. (2021) observed that male students in Poland were more affected by stereotype threat in language domains than female students. In classroom contexts, Eğitim (2024) reported that foreign English teachers in Japan often face phenotypical, gender-based, and personality-based stereotypes, while critical cultural competence activities have proven effective in raising learners' cultural awareness. Biondo Salomão (2019) found, in a study of virtual collaborative environments, that well-structured teletandem sessions can facilitate positive changes in cultural and linguistic beliefs among Brazilian teachers and their colleagues from Uruguay and Argentina. Research by Koenig et al. (2023) with German primary school children did not find a significant effect of stereotype threat on word learning, suggesting that factors such as motivation may be influential.

Deutschmann and Steinvall (2020) employed paired-guess techniques in the RAVE and CRAVE projects in Sweden to raise awareness of linguistic stereotypes, demonstrating that voice gender and accent influence individuals' perceptions. Nikitina et al. (2015) examined "big country" and "cold country" stereotypes among Russian learners in Malaysia, highlighting the need to consider such representations in cultural education. Bedyńska et al. (2020) provided evidence that stereotype threat can undermine academic success by diminishing working memory and fostering intellectual helplessness. Makoelle (2020) found that inclusive education rhetoric in Kazakhstan still employs exclusionary Soviet-era terms, which perpetuate social stereotypes. Similarly, Minguez Lopez (2017) found that Catalan literature for children and adolescents frequently relies on cultural stereotypes, raising questions about the authenticity of multicultural representation. Issakova et al. (2023) conducted a cross-cultural analysis of ethnic stereotypes in jokes, demonstrating that both universal and culturally specific patterns are at play.

This review of the literature demonstrates that stereotypes affect language acquisition through a complex interplay of pedagogical, psychological, cultural, and social mechanisms. Both theoretical and practical considerations underscore the importance of addressing stereotypes within foreign language education. Studies specifically analysing the prejudices and stereotypes held by German language learners in Turkey remain extremely limited. While the majority of prior research has focused on general language attitudes or secondary school students, little attention has been given to the mental representations and stereotypes of university-level teacher candidates. By investigating the perceptions of prospective German teachers, the present study addresses this important gap and contributes to a richer understanding of language attitudes, stereotypes, and teacher identity (Kramsch, 1993; Dörnyei & Csizér, 2002). Given that pre-service teachers are not only language learners but also future cultural mediators, examining their perceptions and stereotypes is crucial for enhancing language teaching curricula and promoting intercultural sensitivity. Accordingly, this study seeks to fill an important gap in the literature by systematically analyzing the stereotypes and perceptions of Germany and the German language among prospective German teachers at Turkish universities. In doing so, it aims to contribute to both the academic literature and the development of more culturally responsive language teaching practices.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This study aims to comprehensively examine the individual and socially constructed perceptions of prospective German teachers in Turkey regarding Germany. To achieve this, a phenomenological design was employed—a primary approach in qualitative research. Phenomenological design seeks to describe the essence of a phenomenon as experienced by individuals, focusing on their conscious perceptions and the core meanings of these lived experiences (Creswell, 2013). As Creswell (2013) asserts, this research model is particularly suitable for capturing the meanings of experiences shared by individuals. In this context, the phenomenological approach was chosen to illuminate how prospective German teachers' perceptions of Germany are shaped and internalized based on personal experience and perceptual structures influenced by broader social imagery.

2.2. Participants

The participants were undergraduate students enrolled in the Department of German Language Teaching at a university in Turkey. A total of 21 pre-service German teachers participated in the study. According to Polkinghorne (1989, as cited in Creswell, 2013), phenomenological studies should include a minimum of five and a maximum of 25 participants who can comprehensively represent the phenomenon under investigation. Thus, the sample size in this research aligns with established principles of phenomenological inquiry. To provide a comprehensive overview of the study group, relevant demographic information was collected and analyzed: Among the 21 participants, 15 were female and six were male, spanning all four undergraduate year levels. None of the participants reported a German-speaking background, meaning none had lived in Germany or spoken German as a family language in their daily life.

2.3. Data Collection Instrument

A semi-structured interview form was utilized as the primary data collection instrument to elicit in-depth perceptions of prospective German teachers regarding Germany. This method is widely recognized in qualitative research for combining the structure of a guided interview protocol with the flexibility to explore emergent themes arising during the interaction (Albaret & Deas, 2023). The interview questions were designed following a review of relevant national

and international literature, ensuring that they were grounded in a robust scientific foundation. This literature review provided extensive background information on the cultural and social factors shaping participants' perceptions. The questions were crafted to encourage participants to articulate both their positive and negative images of Germany, the sources underlying these views, and how such perceptions influenced their own learning processes. Consistent with the phenomenological orientation of the study, the aim was to probe the individual experiences and perception patterns of the participants in greater depth. To ensure content validity, the interview protocol was reviewed by three field experts. Based on their evaluations, the final version was structured to capture the participants' experiences and perceptions.

2.4. Data Collection

Data collection was conducted voluntarily. All German Language Teaching students were informed about the study's purpose and scope, and individual interviews were scheduled with students who volunteered to participate. Interview appointments were arranged in consultation with participants, taking into account their schedules. Interviews were conducted in a quiet, distraction-free environment to ensure participants' comfort and privacy. All interviews were audio recorded, with participants' consent, and each session lasted approximately 30 minutes. Upon completion, the recordings were fully transcribed for analysis. Several strategies—such as triangulation, member checking, and peer debriefing—were implemented to ensure the trustworthiness of the qualitative data; these procedures are described in detail in the section on validity and reliability below. Ethical principles were strictly adhered to throughout the research process. Participants were fully informed that their participation was voluntary, that they could withdraw at any time, and that all data would be used exclusively for scholarly purposes. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the data collection process was formally documented.

2.5. Data Analysis

Data analysis commenced with the verbatim transcription of all audio-recorded interviews. The researcher familiarized themselves with the transcripts by reading them multiple times, making initial notes on salient features such as language use, contextual emphasis, conceptual definitions, and abstract expressions. The transcripts and accompanying notes were then analyzed collectively, and meaningful themes reflecting the participants' experiences were identified. Themes were categorized according to their similarities and differences, and, where appropriate, certain themes were renamed or excluded in alignment with the study's objectives. Once the individual analyses were completed, the typical patterns across participants were synthesized, and central themes and supporting sub-themes were constructed. In the final stage, the analysis was enriched with direct statements from participants, providing a deeper understanding of pre-service German teachers' perceptions of Germany.

2.6. Validity and Reliability

Multiple strategies were adopted to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings. First, member checking was used: the interview transcripts were shared with participants, who were invited to verify the accuracy and completeness of the content. None of the participants requested changes, supporting the study's confirmability, authenticity, and content validation (Hays & Singh, 2022). Additionally, the identified themes were shared with participants to verify that they accurately represented their experiences. To enhance reliability, a triangulation approach was employed, involving systematic, independent, and repeated cycles of data analysis. Each coder independently developed codes based on the interview

transcripts, after which a common codebook was established. An independent external reviewer was engaged further to strengthen the internal consistency and validity of the findings. This auditor critically examined the codebook and emergent findings, offering recommendations as needed. This external review process significantly enhanced the reliability and accuracy of the study's results (Hays & Singh, 2022).

3. Findings

This section presents the qualitative findings regarding the perceptions and attitudes of the participating students towards Germany, systematically structured according to themes, sub-themes, and codes identified through content analysis. The results are illustrated with direct statements from participants. The participants' perceptions of Germany were organized into two overarching themes: Positive views about Germany and negative views about Germany.

3.1. Positive Views about Germany

The positive theme was further divided into five sub-themes, each representing distinct dimensions of the students' perceptions and experiences.

3.1.1. Educational opportunities and academic quality

A significant number of participants ($n = 11$) emphasized the appeal of Germany's free higher education, the accessibility and stability of its educational system, and the discipline associated with German universities. One participant remarked, "Since studying in Germany is free, my academic dream is attached to it." Another observed, "The German education system is very organized and planned, which attracts me." Such statements highlight how Germany's structured academic environment is viewed as a pathway for personal and professional development, placing the country at the center of prospective teachers' long-term aspirations.

3.1.2. Standard of living and order

The sub-theme "standard of living and order" ($n=10$) focused on Germany's safety, punctuality, and cleanliness. Participants described Germany as "a place where everything is in accordance with the rules" and highlighted the reliability of public life. For example, one student noted, "Everything runs like clockwork there, there is no chaos," while another added, "Germany is very clean and safe, so I would like to live there." These accounts reflect the importance of public order and reliability in the participants' idealization of Germany.

3.1.3. Cultural respect and tolerance

Participants also expressed appreciation for Germany's multicultural environment and respect for individual freedoms ($n = 8$). Statements such as "No one bothers the other, everyone respects each other," and "The greeting culture is pervasive, I like that very much," underscore the perceived coexistence of diverse cultures and widespread politeness in German society.

3.1.4. Economic power and job opportunities

Economic advantages emerged as a central theme ($n = 14$), including high salaries, low unemployment, robust employee rights, and affordable goods. A participant observed, "You can even make a living on the minimum wage, which is not possible in Turkey," and another highlighted, "Cars are very cheap in Germany, so I would like to live there." These

perspectives suggest that perceptions of economic prosperity and security have a significant influence on participants' attitudes toward Germany.

3.1.5. Technology and environmental awareness

Participants also identified Germany's advanced technological infrastructure and strong environmental consciousness as positive attributes (n = 9). Statements such as "They separate their rubbish, they are environmentally conscious," and "Germans are very productive, they invest in technology," were common. These aspects contribute to Germany's overall positive image among future teachers of German. In summary, economic prosperity (n = 14), the quality of the education system (n = 11), and high living standards (n = 10) emerged as the most significant positive factors motivating the participants' interest in Germany.

3.2. Negative Views about Germany

In addition to these positive expectations, participants reported several concerns regarding life in Germany, grouped into four sub-themes: feelings of racism and exclusion, cold social relationships, climatic conditions, and language problems.

3.2.1. Feelings of racism and exclusion

A prominent negative perception among participants (n=10) was the fear of racism and social exclusion, particularly as Turkish nationals in Germany. One participant stated, "I am afraid of being excluded because I am Turkish," while another noted, "Foreigners can be perceived as a threat." Such concerns reflect a sense of vulnerability and insecurity that can overshadow otherwise positive impressions of the country.

3.2.2. Cold social relationships

The most frequently mentioned negative theme was the perception of "cold social relationships" (n = 12). Participants described German society as emotionally distant, individualistic, and lacking strong interpersonal bonds. Typical comments included, "There is no sense of neighbourhood, people are distant," and "I am afraid I will not be able to have honest conversations." These findings suggest that concerns about social integration and the lack of a sense of community significantly influence students' perceptions.

3.2.3. Climatic conditions

Environmental factors also contributed to the formation of negative perceptions (n = 4). Participants often described Germany as "cloudy and rainy," or "foggy," and expressed concerns that the cold weather would be challenging and negatively affect comfort and well-being.

3.2.4. Language problems

Language-related challenges (n = 3) were another source of concern. Participants highlighted the perceived difficulty of German grammar and pronunciation, as well as challenges in memorizing articles. Typical statements included, "Grammar is complicated," "Pronunciation difficulty," and "It is very difficult to remember the articles, it is difficult for me." Although mentioned less frequently, these challenges still contributed to participants' negative views of Germany and were seen as barriers to adaptation and academic success. The analysis of data from 21 participants revealed a distinctly bipolar perception of Germany. While the country is viewed as attractive—due to education, economic strength, and

environmental consciousness—it simultaneously evokes fears related to racism, cold social relationships, climate, and language difficulties. These findings illustrate the complexity and ambivalence of the mental representations held by future German teachers.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that prospective German teachers in Turkey possess complex and ambivalent perceptions of Germany. These perceptions are shaped by a dynamic interplay of admiration and concern, resulting in a multidimensional image of the target country. On one hand, Germany is seen as a highly desirable destination, primarily due to its economic strength, well-organized education system, high standard of living, and commitment to environmental sustainability. On the other hand, significant concerns persist, including emotional distance in social relationships, apprehension about discrimination and exclusion, challenging climatic conditions, and perceived linguistic barriers.

Among the positive perceptions, economic opportunities ($n = 14$), the quality and accessibility of education ($n = 11$), and public order and safety ($n = 10$) emerged as dominant themes, positioning Germany as an aspirational setting for the participants' academic and professional futures. These findings suggest that Germany represents more than just a place for language acquisition; it embodies ideals of personal growth and career fulfilment. Conversely, negative perceptions such as “cold social relationships” ($n = 12$) and “feelings of exclusion and racism” ($n = 10$) indicate that participants also associate Germany with socio-emotional challenges that may complicate integration and belonging. The coexistence of these positive and negative perceptions highlights a distinctly bipolar representation of Germany—one that fuses opportunity with unease. This duality highlights a crucial implication: the mental representations that prospective foreign language teachers construct about the target society extend beyond linguistic aspects, being profoundly shaped by cultural, social, and emotional dimensions. Such results reinforce the need to embed cultural awareness, critical reflection, and stereotype literacy more explicitly within teacher education programs. Equipping future teachers with these competencies will enable them to approach the target culture with balanced, well-informed, and empathetic understanding, free from both uncritical idealization and prejudice.

In summary, this study advances our understanding of how prospective teachers perceive the target culture and provides practical insights for foreign language pedagogy. Intercultural competence should be established as a core pillar in language teacher education, and future research should continue to explore how perceptions evolve into productive intercultural attitudes. Longitudinal, comparative, and intervention-based research designs are particularly recommended to further illuminate the development and transformation of these mental representations within teacher education curricula. This research reveals that the perceptions of prospective German teachers in Turkey are multifaceted and often ambivalent, shaped by a complex interaction of personal experiences, societal narratives, and educational exposure. These perceptions—spanning from admiration for Germany's economic and educational systems to concerns regarding social exclusion and cultural distance—emphasize the vital role of cultural awareness in teacher education.

These results are consistent with Arıkan's (2011) study, which showed that prospective language teachers' perceptions of the target culture are closely linked to their socioeconomic background. Arıkan (2011) found that teacher training students with higher socioeconomic status and greater familiarity with cultural content generally developed a more positive attitude towards the target culture. In contrast, those with limited cultural knowledge often had negative

or superficial perceptions. Similarly, the present study shows how participants' perceptions of Germany reflect a combination of admiration and concern, influenced by individual experiences and social factors. This highlights the importance of considering socioeconomic and cultural dynamics in teacher training to promote intercultural sensitivity. The findings highlight that the development of intercultural competence is central to shaping future language teachers' attitudes toward the target culture. As Bektaş-Çetinkaya (2014) notes, fostering intercultural sensitivity among pre-service language teachers requires not only subject-matter knowledge but also critical self-reflection on cultural representations. The present study corroborates this, demonstrating that participants, while expressing admiration for many facets of German society, also articulated anxieties rooted in personal fears and broader social discourses, such as concerns over racism and exclusion. As Zorba (2023) points out, a text-based approach to language teaching can significantly improve learners' intercultural awareness by encouraging them to engage critically and reflectively with authentic texts. This approach not only helps learners develop a deeper understanding of the target culture but also enables them to critically question their own cultural perspectives and effectively recognise and challenge stereotypical ideas. These findings are closely related to the current study, in which participants expressed both positive and negative stereotypes about Germany – perceptions that should be critically questioned and reflected upon through targeted cultural education.

These conclusions are further supported by the work of Saygı and Köksal (2024), who found that targeted intercultural competence training at the secondary school level enhanced learners' sensitivity to cultural diversity. This underscores that integrating the discussion of cultural perceptions into teacher education is not a supplementary aspect but a fundamental necessity, particularly since future teachers play a pivotal role in shaping learners' attitudes towards both the language and its associated cultures. The debate on intercultural competence in Turkey must also consider the country's unique position between Western and non-Western cultural paradigms. Zorba (2025) argues that Turkish language teaching often vacillates between adopting Western-influenced models of interculturality and maintaining indigenous perspectives. He advocates for context-sensitive pedagogical approaches that consider both global frameworks and local realities.

A notable concern expressed by participants was the insufficient representation of culture in instructional materials, echoing the observations of Arıkan (2009), who found that many prospective EFL teachers considered their textbooks to lack substantive coverage of the target culture. Without exposure to nuanced and authentic cultural content during their training, future teachers risk retaining superficial or stereotyped perceptions. Therefore, teaching materials in foreign language education must be enriched with authentic, diverse, and critically engaging cultural content. Recent research findings show that it remains challenging to develop intercultural awareness among language learners in Turkey. Zorba and Çakır (2019) found that English textbooks commonly used in Turkish schools present cultural elements in a fragmented and sometimes inaccurate manner, and that grammar-oriented teaching further limits students' ability to develop intercultural understanding. Their intervention study showed that explicit, activity-based training in intercultural awareness significantly improved students' cultural knowledge, comparative skills, and interest in other cultures. These findings underscore the need to move beyond textbook-oriented, grammar-based approaches and integrate interactive, culture-oriented activities into language teacher training. The findings of Zorba and Çakır (2019), therefore, confirm the recommendations of the present study to enrich materials and pedagogical practices with authentic and critical cultural content.

Based on these insights, the following recommendations are proposed. Teacher education programs should embed intercultural competence as a core component, enabling students to reflect on their own cultural assumptions while appreciating and critically evaluating the perspectives of others. Educational environments should provide structured opportunities for pre-service teachers to discuss and deconstruct cultural stereotypes openly and honestly. This fosters professional growth and equips them to approach language teaching with cultural responsibility. Curriculum designers should review and revise textbooks and teaching resources to reflect the complexity of German-speaking societies more accurately. The inclusion of real-life narratives, contemporary issues, and diverse voices can help prevent the perpetuation of simplistic or outdated cultural representations. Exchange programs, tandem partnerships, and virtual intercultural encounters should be encouraged to offer future teachers first-hand experience, fostering empathy and openness—qualities essential for effective language teaching. Future studies should investigate how cultural perceptions evolve throughout teacher education and how they influence actual teaching practices. Comparative research across universities and regions, as well as longitudinal and intervention-based studies, is particularly needed to deepen our understanding of how cultural perceptions are constructed and transformed. In conclusion, this study highlights the need to redefine the role of culture in foreign language education. Beyond the teaching of grammar and vocabulary, language education must engage learners in understanding the social, emotional, and symbolic dimensions of language. In doing so, prospective teachers will be better prepared to serve as culturally responsive educators and mediators within increasingly diverse and globalized classrooms.

Ethical Issues

The author declares that this study was conducted in strict accordance with established ethical standards of COPE. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the data collection procedures were systematically documented.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

- Abrams, Z.I. (2002). Surfing to cross-cultural awareness: Using internet-mediated projects to explore cultural stereotypes. *Foreign Language Annals*, 35, 141–160. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-9720.2002.tb03151.x>
- Akıllılar, T. (2013). İkinci yabancı dil olarak Almanca öğreniminde üstbilişsel farkındalık. *Uşak Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 6, 282–291. <https://doi.org/10.12739/USOSBD.2013.6.ÖYGE.282>
- Albaret, M., & Deas, J. (2023). Semi-structured interviews. In F. Badache, L. R. Kimber, & L. Maertens (Eds.), *International organizations and research methods: An introduction* (pp. 82–89). USA: University of Michigan Press.
- Allport, G.W. (1954). *The nature of prejudice*. USA: Addison-Wesley.
- Altunya, N. (2006). *Gazi Eğitim Enstitüsü 1926-1980*. Ankara: Gazi Üniversitesi Yayınları.
- Arikan, A. (2009). Problems with coursebooks in EFL classrooms: Prospective teachers' opinions. *EKEV Academic Review*, 38, 309–317.
- Arikan, A. (2011). Prospective English language teachers' perceptions of the target language and culture in relation to their socioeconomic status. *English Language Teaching*, 4(3), 232–242. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v4n3p232>

- Armaoğlu, F. (2009). *20. yüzyıl siyasi tarihi*. İstanbul: Alkım Yayınevi.
- Aydın, A. (2017). Türkiye-Almanya dostluk antlaşması (3 Mart 1924). *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 19(1), 107–121. <https://doi.org/10.5578/jss.54087>
- Balcı, S. (2008). Osmanlı Devleti'nde modernleşme girişimlerine bir örnek: Lisan mektebi. *Tarih Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 27(44), 77–98. https://doi.org/10.1501/Tarar_0000000410
- Balcı, U. (2016). Anadolu liselerinde ikinci yabancı dil olarak Almanca eğitimi: Batman ili örneği. *Dicle Üniversitesi Ziya Gökalp Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 29, 334–341. <https://doi.org/10.14582/DUZGEF.757>
- Bedyńska, S., Krejtz, I., Rycielski, P., & Sędek, G. (2020). Stereotype threat is linked to Language achievement and domain identification in young males: Working memory and intellectual helplessness as mediators. *Psychology in the Schools*, 57(9), 1331–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.22413>
- Bedyńska, S., Rycielski, P., & Jabłońska, M. (2021). Measuring stereotype threat at math and language arts in secondary school: Validation of a questionnaire. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 553964. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.553964>
- Bektaş-Çetinkaya, Y. (2014). Extension of teacher knowledge: developing the intercultural competence of pre-service foreign-language teachers in Turkey. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 8(2), 153–168.
- Biondo Salomão, A. C. (2019). Teletandem and teachers' beliefs about culture and language: Deconstruction or reinforcement of stereotypes? *International Journal of Computer-Assisted Language Learning and Teaching*, 9(1), 1–18. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4018/IJCALLT.2019010101>
- Çakır, M. (2012). The image of Turks in German culture. In Z. Gülmüş (Ed.), *Almanya Türkleri: On the 50th anniversary of the Turkish-German labor agreement* (pp. 27–52). Eskişehir: Anadolu University Press.
- Can, D. (2020). *Almanca öğretmen adaylarının öz yeterlilik inançlarının ve mesleki tutumlarının incelenmesi* (Publication no. 624453) [MA Thesis, Atatürk University]. National Thesis Center.
- Canver, O. C. (2008). *Otuzybeş yıllık göç ve bürokrasi tanıklıklarım*. Ankara:Phoenix Yayınevi.
- Cenoz, J., & Gorter, D. (2011). Focus on multilingualism: A study of trilingual writing. *The Modern Language Journal*, 95(3), 356–369. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2011.01206.x>
- Commission of the European Communities. (2003). *Promoting language learning and linguistic diversity: An action plan 2004–2006*. Brussels: Commission of the European Communities.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Davison, R. H. (1961). Westernized education in Ottoman Turkey. *Middle East Journal*, 15(3), 289–301.
- Demirel, Ö. F. (2021). Yüksek ziraat enstitüsü'nün kuruluş yıllarında Almanca dersleri, okutmanları ve öğretim yöntemleri. *Diyalog Interkulturelle Zeitschrift Für Germanistik*, 9(1), 122–144. <https://doi.org/10.37583/diyalog.958480>
- Deutschmann, M., & Steinvall, A. (2020). Combatting linguistic stereotyping and prejudice by evoking stereotypes. *Open Linguistics*, 6(1), 651–671. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opli-2020-0036>
- Dörnyei, Z., & Csizer, K. (2002). Motivational dynamics in second language acquisition: Results. *Applied Linguistics*, 23, 421–462. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/23.4.421>

- Dovidio, J. F., Hewstone, M., Glick, P., & Esses, V. M. (Eds.). (2010). *The Sage handbook of prejudice, stereotyping and discrimination*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Eğitim, S. (2024). Voices on language teacher stereotypes: Critical cultural competence building as a pedagogical strategy. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 23(6), 925–939. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2022.2070847>
- Garrett, P. (2010). *Attitudes to language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Genel, M. (2014). Almanya'ya giden ilk Türk işçi göçünün Türk basınındaki izdüşümü "Sirkeci Garı'ndan Munchen Hauptbahnhof'a". *Selçuk İletişim*, 8(3), 301–338. <https://doi.org/10.18094/si.37255>
- Güngördü, O. B. (2019). Türk romanında II. Dünya Savaşı dönemi Almanya'sı imgesi. *Bilig*, 89, 121–142. <https://doi.org/10.12995/bilig.8906>
- Hays, D. G., & Singh, A. A. (2022). *Qualitative inquiry in counseling and education*. USA: Cognella Academic Publishing.
- Hekimler, O. (2023). Türkiye-Almanya ilişkilerinde nasyonal sosyalist Almanya'dan Türkiye'ye sığınan aydınların etkisi. *Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 21, 876–898. <https://doi.org/10.35408/comuybd.1345703>
- Işık, S. G., Altıntuğ, F. A., Birkollu, S. S., & Güneylı, A. (2024). Understanding university students' foreign language learning attitudes: An analysis based on stereotypes. *Societies*, 14(9), 169. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc14090169>
- Issakova, S. S., Kultanbayeva, N. K., Tukhtarova, A. S., Zhetessova, Z. A., & Kartzhan, N. Ye. (2023). Linguocultural analysis of ethnic stereotypes in humorous discourse: A comparative analysis. *Eurasian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 9(3), 33–47. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32601/ejal.903004>
- Karaman, F. (2017). Temel eğitimde ikinci yabancı dil olarak Almanca öğretimi. *Batman Üniversitesi Yaşam Bilimleri Dergisi*, 7(2/1), 104–110.
- Kocadoru, Y. (2004). Yüksel Pazarkaya ve Nevfel Cumart'ın şiirlerindeki Almanya imgelerinin karşılaştırılması. *Osmangazi Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 5(1), 67–74.
- Kocaman Wilutzki, S. (2023). Gurbet – Die Fremde: Almanya'ya göçün 60'ıncı yılında Türkiye'den Almanya'ya giden ilk kuşak. *Senectus*, 1(1), 67–90. <https://doi.org/10.26650/senectus.2023.1.1.0006>
- Koenig, S., Stang-Rabrig, J., Hannover, B., Zander, L., & McElvany, N. (2023). Stereotype threat in learning situations? An investigation among language minority students. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 38(2), 841–864. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10212-022-00618-9>
- Kramersch, C. (1993). *Context and culture in language teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kreiser, K. & Neumann, C. K. (2009). *Kleine Geschichte der Türkei*. Ditzingen: Reclam Verlag.
- Krieglmeyer, R., & Sherman, J. W. (2012). Disentangling stereotype activation and stereotype application in the stereotype misperception task. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 103(2), 205–224. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0028764>
- Makoelle, T. M. (2020). Language, terminology, and inclusive education: A case of Kazakhstani transition to inclusion. *Sage Open*, 10(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020902089>
- Minguez López, X. (2017). The maze of stereotyping in Catalan children's and young people's literature. *Didáctica. Lengua y Literatura*, 29, 173–187. <https://doi.org/10.5209/DIDA.57136>
- Nikitina, L., Don, Z. B. M., & Cheong, L. S. (2015). Exploring structure and salience of stereotypes about Russia. *Zeitschrift für Slavistik*, 60(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1515/slav-2015-0001>

- Nikitina, L., Tan, R.H., & Mohamad, J. (2022). Malaysian university students' mental images of Portuguese-speaking countries and their motivations to learn Portuguese. *Moderna Språk*, 116, 140–166. <https://doi.org/10.58221/mosp.v116i2.12232>
- Özgüldür, Y. (1993). *Türk-Alman ilişkileri (1923-1945)*. Ankara: Genelkurmay Basımevi.
- Özil, Ş. (2013). Kolloquium / Konferans: Türkiye Almanya- Migration und Interkulturalität im Regionalen Kontext / bölgesel bağlamda göç ve kültürlerarası iletişim. *Studien Zur Deutschen Sprache Und Literatur*, 1(29), 103–107.
- Paladino, M.-P., Poddesu, L., Rauzi, M., Vaes, J., Cadinu, M., & Forer, D. (2009). Second language competence in the Italian-speaking population of Alto Adige/Südtirol: Evidence for linguistic stereotype threat. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 28(3), 222–243. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X09335333>
- Polkinghorne, D. E. (1989). Phenomenological research methods. In R. S. Valle & S. Halling (Eds.), *Existential-phenomenological perspectives in psychology* (pp. 41–60). New York: Plenum.
- Sayer, P., & Meadows, B. (2012). Teaching culture beyond nationalist boundaries: National identities, stereotyping, and culture in language education. *Intercultural Education*, 23(3), 265–279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14675986.2012.702446>
- Saygi, G., & Köksal, D. (2024). Investigating the impact of intercultural communicative competence training at high school setting. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(2), 204–219. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13861245>
- Spencer-Rodgers, J. (2001). Consensual and individual stereotypic beliefs about international students among American host nationals. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 25(6), 639–657. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767\(01\)00029-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0147-1767(01)00029-3)
- Tapan, N., & Kuruyazıcı, N. (2020). İstanbul Üniversitesi Almanca bölümlerinin kuruluşundan günümüze gelişim süreci. *Diyalog, Sonderausgabe: 85 Jahre Germanistik in der Türkei* (Special Issue), 223–231.
- Tinsley, T., & Board, K. (2013). *Languages for the future*. UK: British Council. https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/languages_for_the_future_2017.pdf
- Üstün, B., & Tanrıku, L. (2023). Ein statistischer Vergleich der in türkischen Universitäten angebotenen Abteilungen für Deutschlehrausbildung, Germanistik und Übersetzungswissenschaften Deutsch. In N. Demiryay (Ed.), *International research in education sciences V* (pp. 9–43). Ankara: Eğitim Yayınevi.
- Zorba, M. G. (2023). A text-based approach to developing EFL learners' intercultural awareness in higher education. *Turkish Journal of Education*, 12(2), 106–121. <https://doi.org/10.19128/turje.1186875>
- Zorba, M. G. (2025). (Re)locating Türkiye's intercultural stance through juxtaposing non-Western and Western perspectives. *Intercultural Communication Education and Research in the Middle East and North Africa* (pp. 66–84), London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003588993>
- Zorba, M. G., & Çakır, A. (2019). A case study on intercultural awareness of lower secondary school students in Turkey. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 13(1), 62–83.